

SELF -DETERMINATION OF A HUMAN AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7707927>

Abstract. *In the development of the personality of a teenager, morality, a specific consciousness, is of particular importance. When shaping the personality of a teenager, it is necessary to take into account his attitude to the environment, social phenomena, people.*

The article deals with the definition of the concept of "professional self-determination". Professional self-determination is considered in scientific research as an integral and essential component of the professional development of a person.

Keywords: *professional self-determination, social maturity, human life, responsibility.*

In our country, a lot of work to build an independent legal democratic state and a free civil society is aimed at realizing its potential for self-realization and creating conditions for training morally healthy, intellectually, intellectually and practically mature personnel.

In the process of education, the formation of a person's worldview is enriched along with certain knowledge. The student's worldview and knowledge change in the following cases, firstly, as a result of the influence of the external social environment; secondly, through a number of special and formal organizations and institutions, etc., directly shaping worldviews and knowledge.

Erickson analyzes in detail the psychological mechanisms of self-awareness in adolescents, in which he explains the manifestation of a new sense of time, psychosexual interest, pathogenic (disease-causing) processes and their various manifestations.

L.I. Bozhovich divides personality formation into certain periods depending on motives, so this approach can be called motivational. According to L.I. Bozhovich, the formation of a person consists of the following stages: the first stage - infancy - from birth to 1 year; the second stage - motivational imagination - from 1 to 3 years; the third stage - the period of awareness of "I" - from 3 to 7 years; the fourth stage - the period of self-awareness as a social being - from 7 to 11 years; the fifth stage: a) the period of self-consciousness - from 12 to 14 years; b) the period of determining (finding) one's place - from 15 to 17 years (1).

E. Spranger in his book "Psychology of adolescence" recommends entering adolescence for girls from 13 to 19 years old, and for boys from 14 to 22 years old. According to E. Spranger, the main changes that occur during this age period are: personal "discovery of oneself"; increased reflection; awareness (understanding) of one's individuality and recognition of personal characteristics; the emergence of good life plans; d) determine the way of organizing one's personal life, etc. In his opinion, the essence of the crisis that occurs in 14-17-year-olds lies in the feeling of getting rid of the childish attitude of adults. Another characteristic of the age of 17-21 is the emergence of a crisis of isolation and isolation from peers and society. This situation is due to historical conditions and factors. E. Spranger, K. Burov, A. Maslow and others are considered major representatives of the personological theory [2; 3; 4].

Adolescence is a period in which worldviews, beliefs, views, principles, self-awareness, assessments, etc. are formed. If a child of primary school age acts on the instructions of adults or

according to his random, involuntary desires, the teenager begins to organize his activities on the basis of certain principles, beliefs and personal views. In the development of the personality of a teenager, morality, a specific consciousness, is of particular importance. When shaping the personality of a teenager, it is necessary to take into account his attitude to the environment, social phenomena, people.

During this period, entry into interpersonal relationships, the child's personal reaction to micro- and macro-environmental features and situations, the ability to distinguish between similarities and differences between them means his growth. Until the process of expressing and explaining things and events with words takes place, simple knowledge of nature and society is realized through behavior, behavior, action. For the same reason, the period of individuality, as one of the first stages of growing up, prepares a solid foundation for self-realization.

The human age begins with self-awareness and ends with a process of physical, mental and social maturity. This period differs from other periods of development in the perfect acquisition of human characteristics as a member of an ethnic group. Distinctive features are reflected in the following, and it consists of two stages:

- I. From the appearance of speech to 6-7 years:
 - that the child has a spatial balance;
 - the presence of a period of "I", consisting of self-consciousness;
 - the birth of the opportunity to effectively use the richness of the native language in speech;
 - able to comply with national customs and rules of conduct;
 - acquisition of etiquette, social values;
 - formation of national and universal qualities on the basis of mastering games and other activities;
 - a vivid manifestation of individual typological features;
 - school readiness in all aspects;
 - awareness of training in group cooperation.
- II. Reflection of the characteristics of adolescence:
 - the presence of striving for physical perfection;
 - achievement of typological characteristics in the processes of activity, behavior and relationships;
 - formation of mental, moral, character traits;
 - manifestation of self-awareness in groups of different forms and structures (peers, adults, formal and informal, real);
 - that he has the opportunity to express himself in public life and activities;
 - be active in all aspects of public life;
 - definition of a differentiated attitude to academic subjects; the presence of a certain belief, worldview, personal attitude;
 - Susceptibility to external influences, lack of perseverance in behavior;
 - priority of fantasy and self-construction , etc. [1].

The amount of knowledge acquired at the pre-professional stage is half of what is expected in the remaining years of life. The knowledge that can be mastered in the next period will be enriched, improved and released not in form, but in content and quality. During adolescence, natural opportunities given to a person are realized, socialization and physical growth are accelerated, as a result, solid conditions for growing up are created.

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